

9th International Conference on Data Mining & Knowledge Management Process (CDKP 2020)

July 11 ~ 12 , 2020 , Toronto , Canada
<https://icaita2020.org/cdkp/index.html>

SCOPE & TOPICS

9th International Conference on Data Mining & Knowledge Management Process (CDKP 2020) provides a forum for researchers who address this issue and to present their work in a peer-reviewed forum.

Authors are solicited to contribute to the conference by submitting articles that illustrate research results, projects, surveying works and industrial experiences that describe significant advances in the following areas, but are not limited to these topics only

TOPICS OF INTEREST INCLUDE BUT ARE NOT LIMITED TO THE FOLLOWING :

Data Mining Applications

Parallel and Distributed Data Mining Algorithms, Data Streams Mining, Graph Mining, Spatial Data Mining, Text Video, Multimedia Data Mining, Web Mining, Pre-processing Techniques, Visualization, Security and Information Hiding in Data Mining

Data Mining Foundations

Databases, Bioinformatics, Biometrics, Image Analysis, Financial Modeling, Forecasting, Classification, Clustering, Social Networks, Educational Data Mining

Knowledge Processing

Data and Knowledge Representation, Knowledge Discovery Framework and Process, including pre- and post-processing, Integration of Data Warehousing, OLAP and Data Mining, Integrating Constraints and Knowledge in the KDD Process, Exploring Data Analysis, Inference of Causes, Prediction, Evaluating, Consolidating, and Explaining Discovered Knowledge, Statistical Techniques for Generation a Robust, Consistent Data Model, Interactive Data Exploration/Visualization and Discovery, Languages and Interfaces for Data Mining, Mining Trends, Opportunities and Risks, Mining from Low-quality Information Sources

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers through the [Submission System](#) by **April 18,2020**. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this conference. The proceedings of the conference will be published by [Computer Science Conference Proceedings](#) in [Computer Science & Information Technology \(CS&IT\)](#) series(Confirmed).

Selected papers from CDKP 2020, after further revisions, will be published in the special issue of the following journals

- [International Journal of Database Management Systems \(IJDMS\)](#)
- [International Journal of Data Mining & Knowledge Management Process \(IJDMP\)](#)
- [Information Technology in Industry \(ITII\)New](#)– ESCI(WOS) Indexed

Important dates:

Submission Deadline : April 18,2020

Authors Notification : June 20,2020

Registration & Camera-Ready Paper Due : June 28,2020

Contact us:

Here's where you can reach us : cdkpc@yahoo.com or cdkp@icaita2020.org